

D.3.2 Recommendations for digitalised surveillance systems of severe infectious diseases leading to hospitalisation

UNITED FOR SURVEILLANCE IN EUROPE

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1. Executive summary – Main recommendations

Severe infections **place a significant burden on healthcare systems**, particularly in critical settings such as emergency departments, infectious disease wards with isolation facilities, and intensive care units. Reliable and robust surveillance of these infections is therefore essential, especially during widespread epidemics or pandemics. Importantly, severe infections also serve as **a reliable indicator of disease trends**, as they are less influenced by factors such as testing capacity or individuals' willingness to seek medical care and get tested. An adequate surveillance system for severe infections also enables **ongoing monitoring of vaccine effectiveness**.

In this Joint Action, it became obvious that surveillance of severe infections is carried out in various ways. The member states taking part in Work Package (WP) 3 have different situations, capabilities, and tools for surveillance. In the beginning of this Joint Action, during spring 2023, a survey on the main characteristics of the surveillance systems of severe infections was conducted among the countries participating in WP3. Information was collected for example on the legal basis, coverage, extent of digitalisation, and coding systems used. The survey report is available at <https://zenodo.org/records/14887202>. Based on the results of this survey, eight pilots were designed.

In nearly all countries, the COVID-19 pandemic prompted major surveillance efforts. In some cases, new data sources became available, existing surveillance systems were improved (e.g. through more timely data flows), and valuable experience was gained in data handling and linkage. However, the response to COVID-19 often resulted in ad hoc solutions that could not be adapted for monitoring other infections or situations post-pandemic. In WP3, a joint analysis was conducted to identify the main determinants and drivers behind the improvements observed during the COVID-19 pandemic, as well as the key challenges or obstacles that remained afterwards. More details can be found in the UNITED4Surveillance D1.1 Progress Report in section "3.3 Description of the work WP3: Hospital surveillance", available at <https://zenodo.org/records/15753676>. This information was also considered when planning the pilots, particularly in relation to integration, interoperability, and the digitalisation of health data systems.

In general, even after the improvements brought about by the pandemic, it was evident that the pilot countries were at different stages in their journey towards full digitalisation of healthcare data. The pilots were specifically designed to enhance surveillance systems in each country. In **the Netherlands**, a thorough stakeholder analysis was carried out and in **Norway** all data sources were carefully mapped to be able to make a blueprint of a robust surveillance system. Similar work was carried out in **Slovenia** and in **Poland**, as data models, plans, definitions were produced even though ICT-resources or data ownership/legal issues prevented the actual data linkage. In **Latvia**, piloting led to a well-received electronic notification form, although ICT -resources as well as legal constraints prevented further linkage of the data. The lack of common grounds on the national integrated system led **Italy** to improve surveillance in intensive care units (ICUs) in the Tuscany region. In **Malta** efforts focused on establishing an automated gastrointestinal disease surveillance system using hospital data, liaising with hospital to improve data sharing and standardisation as well as initiating the development of an IT infrastructure that would allow for real-time automated integrated surveillance of infectious diseases. In **Finland**, laboratory and clinical data linkage at the national level was further analysed while work was carried out to update the legal basis for continuous data linkage.

Recommendations

Several general recommendations can be made based on the work in UNITED4Surveillance WP3:

1. Each country should move **from paper-based systems to digitalised** health care data. That will also be the requirement in the European Health Data Space (EHDS) regulation that entered into force in March 2025, of which key parts will enter into application in March 2029. This recommendation is valid irrespective of whether surveillance data is collected from a sentinel or general setting, i.e., from the databases of certain hospitals or from nation-wide registers.
2. To ensure the surveillance system is robust and sustainable in the long term, **it should not rely on manual data entry**. Manual input increases the workload, even when electronic forms are used. Instead, existing digital data—such as electronic health records (EHRs)—should be leveraged, and the notification process should be highly automated. Separate electronic forms may serve as a temporary solution, ideally integrated with existing login systems to avoid the need for additional usernames or passwords. However, it is essential to transition towards full digitalisation. If manual data entry is unavoidable, one way to improve timeliness and coverage is to implement automated pop-up alerts within patient records to remind clinicians of notifiable cases. Another interim approach is partial digitalisation—for example, collecting data from selected hospitals with suitable IT systems (a "sentinel" model).
3. For a surveillance system to be enduring and robust, **a clear and permanent legal framework should be established within national legislation**. Variations in the interpretation of the GDPR among Member States, along with national or regional political influencers and opinion leaders, can impact access to individual-level data and the use of unique identifiers for data linkage in surveillance. Following the COVID-19 pandemic, several pilot countries found that their existing legislation was insufficient—even for the surveillance of severe infectious diseases—highlighting the need for legal updates to support effective surveillance systems. When the European Health Data Space (EHDS2) becomes legally binding for Member States, there will be a strong impetus to establish clear rules and procedures for data access. For these reasons, legal guidance from the EU is also required.
4. Another essential resource that must be secured from the outset is **the IT infrastructure**, which requires careful planning, a well-defined system architecture, and secure data transfer tools. A common challenge in the healthcare sector is the wide variety of software systems in use. Therefore, when monitoring severe infections, it is crucial to identify which IT systems are used in hospitals. Most IT system providers are private companies, and public health authorities often have limited influence over the selection or operation of these systems. However, for EHR-based surveillance to be effective, data structure harmonisation is necessary. A clearly defined, legally mandated data structure enables successful surveillance, even when different software systems are used across the country. If the EHR data is mostly free text, use of AI or natural language processing (NLP) can potentially be leveraged for surveillance purposes.
5. In Member States that relied on EHRs for surveillance, data flows were established during the COVID-19 pandemic. However, due to time constraints, the systems were often implemented without thorough planning resulting in fragile and/or suboptimal infrastructures. After the pandemic, data coverage and timeliness declined as priorities shifted. Consequently, there may be a future need to modernise, standardise, and strengthen these data flows—or "pipelines."
6. It is also recommended to focus on the **most critical data sources** and prioritise their development. To ensure data security and protect privacy, the principle of data minimisation should be applied—using only the minimum dataset necessary to fulfil the surveillance objectives. A minimal data set is

also important given the demanding hospital setting with high administrative burden and staff shortages. Furthermore, access to data should be strictly controlled by clearly defining who can access specific data, maintaining logs of data access, and ensuring, for example, that statistical analysts work only with the data needed for their tasks, rather than having unrestricted access to all registry data. Establishing robust data governance protocols is essential. This includes clearly defined procedures for requesting data access, identifying who makes access decisions, and outlining the criteria for granting permissions.

7. When building or updating the surveillance system, it is important to understand who the main **stakeholders** are and what their roles, responsibilities, and expectations are. Common understanding is built most successfully by in-person meetings. A collaborative and interdisciplinary approach drives progress. Involving stakeholders increases the acceptance of hospital surveillance. Individualised communication plans can be made for successful communication efforts with a thorough understanding of stakeholders and their expectations. If data is collected directly from hospital IT-systems, and surveillance targets are agreed on, focus should be on **actionable data that hospital staff and hospital boards can use**.
8. Systems should be **adaptable for additional surveillance targets**. In addition to respiratory infections, other serious infections should gradually be covered by surveillance. Currently the relevant EU legislation is the Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2018/945 of 22 June 2018, on the communicable diseases and related special health issues to be covered by epidemiological surveillance as well as relevant case definitions.
9. For surveillance purposes, definitions of monitored items can be based on various **coding systems**. While the International Classification of Diseases (ICD) codes are commonly used, other coding systems—such as those designed for financial claims or administrative purposes—may also be applicable. When integrating clinical information from hospitalised patients with microbiological data from the national infectious disease register, several options exist for designing linkage algorithms. These factors influence how cases are defined and determine the accuracy and reliability of the surveillance data. Key considerations include:
 - Whether the hospitalisation and microbiological test can be considered part of the same disease case (based on the timing of the test in relation to the hospital admission)
 - Whether laboratory confirmation is required (syndromic surveillance can be complemented with lab-confirmed outcomes to improve timeliness and completeness of the surveillance system)
 - Which ICD codes are accepted on their own, and which require accompanying laboratory confirmation

Advances in national surveillance of serious infections leading to hospitalisation will have a beneficial effect on the European level of surveillance and reporting. As Member States improve the coverage and timeliness of national data collection, the **reporting of data to ECDC** and EpiPulse Cases also improves.

Impact of Improved Surveillance on Reporting to ECDC:

- Accuracy and Reliability: Enhanced surveillance leads to more accurate and reliable data.
- Timeliness: Faster data collection and real-time or near-real time reporting improve the timeliness of data submission. Advanced technologies reduce the time for data collection and reporting.
- Comprehensiveness: Better surveillance captures a wider range of data, aiding thorough analysis. Improved systems cover broader geographic areas and diverse populations.

EU Level Implications:

- Strengthened Surveillance Network as a result of better data sharing and adoption of best practices.

- Enhanced Public Health Response by early detection and better coordination.
- Improved Compliance and Reporting if EU regulatory requirements are met incl. standardised data.
- Informed Policy Making to support evidence-based decisions and efficient resource allocation.
- Improved Health Outcomes through targeted interventions and continuous monitoring.

Based on the experiences of the piloting countries, help in the legal domain is needed. For example, clear guidance on EU level application of the GDPR is warranted as there are varying interpretations in Member States on what data can be collected and used for infectious diseases surveillance purposes. Perhaps ECDC could offer an expert opinion on this. Forming a group of Member States' National Institutes Data Protection Officers for easier communication of common issues is a good start. Also needed is guidance on EU level on improving the data quality of SARI, to enable complete and valid comparisons between EU Member States and to enhance interoperability. Investigating adoption of the EEHRxF format in preparation of the European Health Data Space (EHDS) could be a step towards facilitating more uniformity.

From Stakeholders to Data Mapping: A Step-by-Step Guide

Mapping was a key component of all pilots for both Task 3.1 and 3.2. The mapping exercises conducted across piloting countries can be effectively organised into a comprehensive list of essential components. Following the logical sequence outlined below, can help to ensure the successful design and development of national surveillance systems for severe infectious diseases. These common components include fundamentals, such as a solid understanding of stakeholders and IT infrastructure. The list then progresses to more specific needs, such as legal considerations and national surveillance requirements, before focusing on detailed data mapping and the availability of existing resources. This structured method ensures that all aspects of designing and developing a national surveillance system with reporting responsibilities to the ECDC are fully covered, facilitating a smooth and efficient workflow for ongoing and future pilots.

While this logical framework provides a comprehensive step-by-step guide, it is important to keep in mind an agile approach to accommodate the varying priorities and contexts of different countries. Not all countries may prioritise the initial steps in the same way, and some countries may have already completed one or several steps. Flexibility is key to addressing unique needs and circumstances. By remaining adaptable and responsive to changing requirements, countries can effectively implement the framework in a manner that best suits their specific situation, ensuring that all critical elements are addressed in a timely and efficient manner.

Box 1: Mapping approach for the design and development of a national surveillance system

Map stakeholders: Understanding who is involved and their roles is crucial as it sets the context for all subsequent mapping activities. For example, identify IT suppliers to help in understanding the technological landscape and dependencies.

Map IT systems: Knowing the systems in place is essential for integrating and mapping data accurately.

Map legal issues/ legislation: Legal considerations must be understood early to ensure compliance throughout the process.

Map needs of national surveillance: National surveillance needs are necessary to provide a framework for what data is necessary and how it should be managed.

Map needs of ECDC: The ECDC requirements are specific and detailed, so understanding these needs helps in aligning with broader regulatory and reporting standards.

Map diagnosis codes used, and lab tests taken: This step involves detailed data mapping, which is informed by the needs identified in the previous steps.

Map data available from existing data sources: Finally, mapping the available data ensures that all identified needs and requirements can be met with the existing resources.

2. Pilot experience, evaluation and recommendations from Task 3.1 – Establish or improve sentinel-based electronic surveillance of serious infectious diseases or syndromes from hospitals in participating Member States

To monitor incidence, trends, and/or disease severity, a sentinel-based system is more than adequate. In addition, it can be used for targeted sampling of cases with a predetermined clinical picture to get more precise information on circulating microbes. By combining microbiological findings with clinical data such as symptoms, diagnoses, treatments and outcomes, severe infections can be characterised in more detail. A sentinel system, either with or without a defined source population, can also function as a preliminary phase for automatised national surveillance.

In **Latvia**, a digital urgent notification form for severe infections was introduced in hospitals, general practitioner practices, and outpatient institutions, and the healthcare professionals were supported through training materials, information sessions, individual consultations, and regular technical assistance. Statistical data on the use of the system was collected throughout the pilot, and feedback from users was gathered to identify needs for improvement. Discussions were held with IT-system providers and laboratories to prepare for future data integration. Legal experts and public health professionals collaborated to draft proposals for amendments to the regulatory framework supporting electronic reporting.

The pilot in the **Netherlands** provided a comprehensive understanding of stakeholders and their roles in SARI surveillance for building a robust SARI surveillance system. Barriers, facilitators, and recommendations identified by Dutch hospitals offer valuable insights for enhancing hospital surveillance. Furthermore, a blueprint for SARI surveillance based on previous experiences and semi-structured interviews of stakeholders was developed.

In **Malta**, the pilot project focused on mapping and linking of hospital and centralised laboratory system data to establish an automated surveillance system for infectious gastrointestinal illness. This highlighted data quality issues and the importance of having adequate surveillance standards and IT-infrastructures to allow for standardisation and analysis of data. Data sharing agreements were established with the state hospital to facilitate data sharing and security. Moreover additional efforts focused at submitted the proposal for “Malta Infectious Diseases Integrated Surveillance System (MIDISS)” that is funded through the EU4Health DG for Surveillance and that will ensure continuity of the Joint Action work through the creation of a IT infrastructure that will allow for real-time automated integrated surveillance of infectious diseases including at hospital level.

In **Slovenia**, the current paper-based national SARI surveillance is set to be replaced by an EHR-based system as part of the broader initiative to implement EHR-based surveillance for infectious diseases. The first draft of the Slovenian EHR-based SARI surveillance protocol has been prepared, outlining objectives, definitions, structured models for hospitals and microbiology laboratories data, coding, planned data flow and envisioned IT solutions. An IT-solution has also been developed to accept real-time data generated during patient hospital admissions and discharges, which will be sent to the national Central Registry of Patient Data. During the pilot follow-up period, activities to implement the national SARI surveillance system will continue under the EU4Health funded project “Digitalisation of the national communicable diseases surveillance system in Slovenia, NSS-SI.”

2.1 Pilot in Latvia

2.1.1. Background & objectives

Latvia previously relied on a structured paper-based form for urgent notification of notifiable diseases, submitted by fax, email, or regular post in addition to a telephone call. While this format met legal requirements and corresponded to historical technical capabilities, the overall process was manual, slow, time consuming, and disconnected from digital health infrastructure. There was also a fairly high risk of losing notification forms, as well as a risk to the protection of personal data.

Ahead of the pilot, a digital urgent notification form had already been introduced on a national level. The pilot did not aim to develop a new tool, but rather to explore how the new digital form could be used routinely in real conditions and integrated into health system workflows.

The main goals of the pilot were to:

- Encourage the use of the digital notification form in hospitals, outpatient settings, and GP practices.
- Provide training and ongoing support to ensure accurate and consistent use.
- Monitor usage and gather feedback to assess practical feasibility.
- Prepare for future system-to-system (S2S) data exchange to reduce double entry.
- Begin work on legal changes to formally recognise the digital notification process.

The pilot focused on surveillance of severe infections requiring hospitalisation and urgent public health response.

2.1.2. Outcome/delivered product

The digital notification form was deployed through Latvia's national e-health portal and EPID surveillance system, allowing real-life testing under routine conditions.

Over 3,000 urgent notifications were submitted by 782 healthcare professionals. Most public hospitals participated, along with several outpatient and primary care providers.

A full support package was provided, including:

- User guides and short training videos.
- Webinars and individual consultations.
- On-site visits to hospitals where needed.

Usage data was reviewed regularly, helping to identify trends and guide follow-up actions. In parallel, technical discussions were held with LIS and HIS vendors to outline next steps for data integration.

To support official recognition of digital reporting and reduce reliance on paper forms, draft legal amendments were prepared to Cabinet Regulation on Procedures for Registration of Infectious Diseases.

2.1.3. Impact

The pilot marked Latvia's first large-scale attempt to use digital urgent notification in both hospital and outpatient care.

Reported benefits included:

- Faster and more consistent surveillance of individual cases.
- Use of a secure, centralised submission platform (e-veselība), improving traceability.
- Reducing the administrative burden on the healthcare sector and costs.

- Closer collaboration among clinicians, public health professionals, IT developers, and legal experts.
- New momentum around interoperability and long-term digital infrastructure planning.
- Better understanding of readiness across institutions, helping shape next steps for scale-up.

2.1.4. Lessons learned

What worked well:

- Institutions that received targeted support tended to report more regularly and with greater confidence.
- The use of existing e-health login credentials made access straightforward for most users.
- The pilot created space for dialogue between key sectors—healthcare, IT, and public health—on shared goals.
- The possibilities for further digitalisation of epidemiological surveillance are better outlined.

Challenges encountered:

- Manual data entry remains burdensome, especially for hospitals facing staff shortages.
- The lack of integration with HIS and LIS systems led to duplicate effort, discouraging use.
- Legal uncertainty in some institutions slowed adoption.
- Healthcare facilities that rarely detect and report infectious disease cases are less able to adapt to the use of a new digital notification platform.
- Limited technical funding restricted opportunities for automation and local adaptations.

Lessons for the future:

- Scaling digital surveillance depends heavily on seamless system-to-system exchange.
- A gradual approach—starting with selected sites and defined data fields—can be more realistic than a national rollout.
- Even partial digitalisation, if supported properly, can significantly improve data quality and timeliness.

2.1.5. Recommendations

- Finalise and adopt proposed legal amendments to recognise digital urgent notification.
- Begin structured planning for S2S integration, starting with institutions involved in the pilot.
- Develop transitional workflows that allow semi-automated data entry where full integration is not yet possible.
- Secure dedicated IT funding to support technical development and user training.
- Continue offering user support through updated training, technical helpdesks, and feedback surveys.
- Set up interagency coordination between CDPC, NHS, and system vendors to guide future development.

2.1.6. Core messages

- Digital urgent notification is viable, trusted, and secure—but a manual burden for data entry by the health professional still remains and must be addressed.
- Long-term success depends on legal clarity, funding, and technical interoperability.
- This pilot created a solid foundation for broader digital surveillance, including future links with labs and national registries.
- Even in complex environments, meaningful progress is possible when legal, technical, and organisational elements are aligned.

2.2 Pilot in the Netherlands

2.2.1. Background & objectives

Aim

The aim of the pilot study is to explore what the minimal requirements are for a robust and sustainable national SARI surveillance system in the view of the most relevant stakeholders in the Netherlands.

Objectives

1. Identify the most relevant stakeholders for SARI surveillance in the Netherlands.
2. Explore the relative position, the degree of influence, interest, and goals of each stakeholder regarding SARI surveillance.
3. Define the preferred requirements for a SARI surveillance system to be valuable and feasible for stakeholders.
4. Map which data are already available for stakeholders that could be used for a future or existing SARI surveillance system, in terms of source systems and data, information standards, technical staff.
5. Identify current practices and the most relevant barriers according to stakeholders in achieving a robust and sustainable national SARI surveillance system.

2.2.2. Outcome/delivered product

Deliverables

- **Stakeholder analysis report**
Our stakeholder analysis provides an updated and comprehensive overview of all relevant stakeholders with their specific roles (decision makers, suppliers, end-users and influencers) in SARI surveillance in the Netherlands since the end of the COVID-19 pandemic.
***Note:** This deliverable was extended with a **force field analysis report** and a **communication plan SARI surveillance**. However, these reports remain confidential.
- **Semi-structured interview stakeholder report**
The conducted semi-structured interviews on infectious disease surveillance in hospitals offer essential insights in the experienced barriers, facilitators, and wishes from the perspective of stakeholders in the hospital setting.
***Note:** This deliverable is also available as a Research Article (*preprint*): [Infectious disease surveillance in Dutch hospitals: what's in it for us?](#) at BMC Health Services Research (*under review*).
- **Blueprint for SARI surveillance based on semi-structured interviews stakeholders and previous experience with setting up sentinel SARI surveillance**
We provide a blueprint based on the most promising scenarios for establishing SARI surveillance in the Netherlands. The two most promising scenarios for establishing SARI surveillance currently in Q4 2024 in the Netherlands are: 1) using case-based data streams on SARI based on financial claim codes (DBC) from the Dutch Hospital Database (DHD) complemented with laboratory outcomes; and 2) using aggregated data streams on SARI based severity-of-disease classification system (APACHE) from the National Intensive Care Evaluation Registry (NICE).
- **Retrospective analysis of ICU data for other syndromes than SARI**

Our retrospective analysis of ICU data for other syndromes than SARI offers insights that could potentially strengthen infectious disease surveillance in Dutch hospitals and thereby improving preparedness for cross-border health threats.

2.2.3. Impact

The SARI communication plan is successfully implemented to guide our interaction with key stakeholders in the field of SARI surveillance in the Netherlands. Using a communication calendar and/or tracker, outlining details on communication method, timing, and target groups, enabled us to achieve a more consistent, structured and efficient interaction with stakeholders. A bi-annual evaluation of the SARI communication plan will provide insights into its impact and effectiveness, helping to identify areas for improvement and optimise stakeholder engagement.

The two most promising scenarios for establishing SARI surveillance in the Netherlands are both currently being rolled out. For scenario A - SARI in ICUs using the NICE registry - we have included 15 out of 70 ICUs as of week 6, 2025. The SARI ICU data will be published on the on the RIVM website starting from week 36, 2025. For scenario B – SARI in wards and ICUs using DHD – one hospital is ready for SARI data transfer according to the developed Blueprint SARI surveillance in the Netherlands. The implementation of the two scenarios has experienced some delays, however, we remain committed to having both data streams operational by 2025. In 2026, we aim to evaluate both scenarios to determine the long-term necessity of maintaining both data streams.

2.2.4. Lessons learned

- **Stakeholder analysis report**

This results in valuable insights, such as: i) newly identified stakeholders, ii) multiple stakeholders having more than one role, and iii) the possibility of clustering stakeholders in groups based on power of influence and interest. This is essential information for determining how and where to inform, involve and/or collaborate with stakeholders for establishing or maintaining SARI surveillance now or in the future. A force field analysis offers additional insights into personal attitudes, involvement, influence, and relationships regarding SARI surveillance, but details are confidential and cannot be disclosed. However, the results of both analyses equally contributed to developing our communication strategy plan for SARI surveillance in the Netherlands. This communication strategy plan, an additional key result of our pilot study, will guide future communication with stakeholders in the field of SARI surveillance. This communication strategy plan will be a dynamic document requiring periodic updates.

- **Semi-structured interview stakeholder report**

The most quoted barriers by the participants are: i) the unclear stakeholder roles and responsibilities; ii) the different interpretation of General Data Protection Regulation; and iii) having insufficient resources and capacity. The most relevant facilitators for SARI surveillance according to participants are: i) obtaining clinically relevant and actionable data (e.g. data that contributes to improving patient quality of care, antibiotic stewardship programs and/or facilitates healthcare innovation); ii) mutually beneficial collaboration; and iii) having sufficient support on multiple decision-making levels (e.g. hospital board, medical department, hospital IT department) and domains (e.g. legal/privacy, technical, capacity, financial). Participants recommend three key actions to establish or maintain robust infectious disease

surveillance in hospitals. The current adjustment of the Public Health Act (Wpg) in the Netherlands could contribute to this. Firstly, public health institutes should focus on clinically relevant actionable surveillance data that impact patient clinical care. This will likely result in improved intrinsic motivation of hospitals to participate in infectious disease surveillance activities and ensure long-term sustainability of the surveillance system. Secondly, all stakeholders should collaboratively define roles and responsibilities in hospital surveillance more clearly (e.g. by organizing informal meeting and round tables with key stakeholders to discuss surveillance objectives, needs and requirements). Providing a legal framework would help hospitals commit to public health tasks to a greater extent, acknowledge their responsibility, and contribute to providing baseline infectious disease data). Finally, public health institutes should benefit from the innovative qualities of hospitals and microbiology laboratories to a greater extent (e.g. implementation of artificial intelligence technologies that can be of added value for both infectious disease surveillance and improving quality of patient care, or using hospital surveillance data as a valuable data base for addressing innovative, clinically relevant research/policy questions).

- **Blueprint for SARI surveillance based on semi-structured interviews with stakeholders and previous experience with setting up sentinel SARI surveillance**

This blueprint may guide key stakeholders, like hospitals and microbiological laboratories, in implementing SARI surveillance in collaboration with the RIVM. In addition, it informs external stakeholders, such as the Dutch Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport, about the status and rollout plans of these two scenarios for SARI surveillance. We expect that both scenarios are operational in 2025, after which an evaluation will determine in 2026 whether both data streams are necessary for representative SARI surveillance in the Netherlands.

- **Retrospective analysis of ICU data for syndromes other than SARI**

To this end, we evaluated the usefulness of APACHE diagnoses codes for the ‘gastrointestinal infections’ syndrome using the NICE registry during a 10-year period. The preliminary results indicate a lack of added value regarding timeliness and completeness of the data compared to the already existing gastrointestinal and zoonosis surveillance systems in the Netherlands. However, we aim to retrospectively explore additional infectious disease syndromes, including healthcare-associated infections and neuro-infectious syndromes, using the NICE registry after the pilot ends.

***Note:** The objective 4 “Mapping available data already available to stakeholders” will not be addressed, due to the limited new input from external stakeholders during semi-structured interviews. However, we have undertaken additional pilot initiatives beyond our initial pilot plan, such as implementing a communication strategy plan for SARI surveillance and retrospective analysis of intensive care unit (ICU) scoring system (APACHE) for potential use in hospital surveillance, other than SARI.

2.2.5. Recommendations

Based on the Dutch pilot study, we recommend:

- to develop a communication strategy plan to guide and enhance future interactions with stakeholders in the field of hospital surveillance.
- to collaboratively define clear roles and responsibilities with all stakeholders regarding hospital surveillance.

- Public Health Institutes to focus on clinically relevant, actionable data that impact clinical patient care when setting up or maintaining hospital surveillance systems.
- Public Health Institutes to leverage the innovative capabilities of hospitals and medical microbiology laboratories when establishing or maintaining hospital surveillance systems.
- Public Health Institutes to develop a blueprint to guide hospitals in implementing a SARI surveillance system and effectively inform external stakeholders about the rollout plan.

2.2.6. Core messages

The core messages from the Dutch pilot study are:

- A comprehensive understanding of stakeholders and their roles in SARI surveillance is essential for building a robust SARI surveillance system.
- Barriers, facilitators, and recommendations identified by Dutch hospitals offer valuable insights for enhancing hospital surveillance.
- A blueprint for SARI surveillance in the Netherlands advances by implementing two promising scenarios.

***Note:** The UNITED4Surveillance (WP3) pilot study report, entitled “Infectious disease surveillance in Dutch hospitals, is also available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/14699054>

2.3 Pilot in Malta

2.3.1. Background & objectives

Project A: Protocol for Implementing an Infectious Gastrointestinal (GI) Surveillance System in Malta

The main aim of the project is to establish a comprehensive, automated surveillance system for infectious GI illnesses in the Maltese islands and assess the burden of GI disease and their impact on hospitalisations.

Additional objectives:

- Map and integrate relevant data sources and variables to support the establishment of a comprehensive surveillance system.
- Identify gaps and challenges in implementing robust surveillance of GI diseases.
- Develop recommendations to enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of GI disease surveillance.
- Generate weekly surveillance reports to support ongoing monitoring of GI illness and to assess burden of GI disease on hospitals.

Project B: Proposal for the establishment of the Malta Infectious Disease Integrated Surveillance System (MIDISS)

The main aim of MIDISS to establish a comprehensive framework for real-time monitoring, early detection, and effective management of public health challenges, thereby fortifying the EU's capacity to safeguard the well-being of its citizens.

Objectives of MIDISS:

- Establish an integrated Public Health Surveillance IT Infrastructure
- Enhance early warning through automated surveillance outputs & signals

2.3.2. Outcome/delivered product

Project A (GI Surveillance)

The main deliverable for this project is a detailed protocol on the implementation of infectious GI illness surveillance in Malta. Mapping of data from the state hospital and centralised laboratory system was conducted to identify the relevant data sources and variables needed. Using unique identifiers data from various sources was linked using R coding and weekly surveillance reports issued to assist in monitoring trends and disease burden.

The protocol provides details on the local context, the methodology used for data mapping, merging and cleaning of data as well as details on the variables, surveillance indicators, case definitions and pathogens under surveillance. The protocol also includes a weekly GI surveillance report template using dummy data. The weekly reports remain confidential but are shared with the main stakeholders to assist in disease monitoring and surveillance activities. The report also highlights the main challenges and limitations faced and provides recommendations on the way forward to enhance surveillance standards and quality.

Project B (MIDISS)

The project focused on developing a proposal for the EU4Health Direct Grant on improving and strengthening national surveillance systems with the main aim of establishing a harmonised and secure interoperable surveillance system that generates a real-time digital data stream that provides the information needed to timely and effectively fight cross-border threats to public health from infectious diseases.

The proposal for MIDISS was submitted in February 2024. Following approval of the grant in May 2024 and prior to the official start date in January 2025, preparatory work was carried out to get stakeholders involved and develop memorandums of understanding for data sharing. Regular internal meetings were held as well as with relevant technical entities to identify the needs and requirements to establish such a platform. The stakeholders from which data would be utilised for surveillance include the Primary Health Care, State hospitals, Blood Bank and the veterinary sectors amongst others.

The project, which is expected to be completed by 2028, highlights the importance of having integrated and secure IT infrastructures in health to allow for real-time automated surveillance to enhance public health preparedness and response.

2.3.3. Impact

Project A (GI Surveillance)

The project served to establish automated weekly surveillance reports for GI pathogens thus assisting in routine monitoring and outbreak detection primarily at national level. The weekly reports also monitor the disease burden from GI pathogens thus supporting timely public health response and guiding policy.

The project served to highlight several gaps and challenges in the current health data quality and IT infrastructure and offers concrete recommendations on addressing the issues and improve surveillance standards. The meetings held with the hospital administration and IT section proved crucial in ensuring that these issues are addressed and improved with the launch of the new PD system in the state hospitals.

Project B (MIDISS)

As part of the United4Surveillance Work Package on Hospital Surveillance Malta has taken an important step towards addressing long-standing gaps in its national infectious disease surveillance capabilities. Through this initiative, Malta identified key national needs to address the challenges faced and helped design the Public Health Surveillance IT Infrastructure of the MIDISS concept.

MIDISS will include the acquisition of a cutting-edge Public Health Surveillance IT infrastructure equipped with automated and secure data loading from various sources, storage in a secure data warehouse, automated data transformation scripts, alongside an intuitive user dashboard for the creation of routine and configurable ad-hoc surveillance outputs. The projects scope aligns with Malta's IT obligations as an EU Member State to bear the responsibility of diligently monitoring and promptly reporting health concerns to the ECDC and other international partners.

The proposed Public Health Surveillance IT Infrastructure will automate the collection, integration, analysis, and reporting of infectious disease data across healthcare settings, in line with EU standards for security, privacy, and interoperability. By contributing to the development of this proposal under United4Surveillance, Malta has laid the groundwork for a resilient, integrated, and sustainable surveillance system that will enhance preparedness efforts as is mandated by the Serious Cross-Border Threats to Health Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2022/2371).

2.3.4. Lessons learned

The initial proposal was intended to pilot a new Patient Dashboard (PD) system to be launched in state hospitals that would allow for systematic inputting of clinical data especially at Casualty Department level. Unfortunately, the launch of the PD system was delayed indefinitely and the pilot project instead focused on establishing a surveillance system for infectious GI illness.

The pilot highlighted data quality issues and the importance of having adequate surveillance standards and IT infrastructures to allow for standardisation and analysis of data. The main challenges encountered include: lack of appropriate and timely ICD-10 coding at hospital level with no coding being available on admission and coding for discharge diagnosis information being inaccurate and delayed; paediatric data still predominantly paper-based on not available in electric format; electronic clinical data inputted primarily in free text. These issues do not allow for standardisation of data and subsequent analysis and automation. In view of this we could not establish a syndromic surveillance system for infectious GI illness and our protocol focused primarily on linking hospital data with laboratory diagnosis. Additional challenges include the considerable delay in the availability of mortality data and cause of death making such information unsuitable for surveillance purposes.

Main challenges faced in the MIDISS proposal include the multitude of data sources from different stakeholders that will feed into MIDISS. These sources all have different data infrastructures which are constantly being updated and that have their own data quality issues. Such systems are independent and lack standardisation of data and interoperability, making it a challenge to merge and analyse data for good quality outputs.

The pilots also highlighted the lack of available resources especially when it comes to data engineers and analysts necessary for the development of robust systems and data quality as well as the lack of awareness amongst stakeholders and healthcare workers on the importance of having good quality and standardised data and appropriate interoperable IT systems to allow for data analysis and surveillance.

Despite the limitations it was still possible to establish a semi-automated system with the current data and infrastructure that is being utilised to generate weekly surveillance reports that are proving very useful for monitoring outbreaks, trends and hospitalisations due to GI illness.

Both projects highlighted the importance of having a robust legal basis to allow for secondary processing of public health data as well as data sharing agreements with hospitals and other relevant stakeholders to ensure cooperation for sharing of data in a secure manner.

The pilots created space for dialogue between key stakeholders – hospital/healthcare, IT, Public Health, Veterinary Directorate on shared goals and vision and served to clearly define Public Health requirements for surveillance and for key stakeholders to appreciate and factor in surveillance needs in their systems.

2.3.5. Recommendations

- Public Health should be at the forefront and a main player in the development of IT infrastructure of health systems to ensure that these capture good quality data that can be linked and analysed in an automated and secure manner in real-time for surveillance purposes and prompt Public Health action.
- With the advent of AI, innovative tools and methods should be explored in order to facilitate and support surveillance activities, such as text mining tools and free-text analysis.
- Need for established surveillance standards and models to assist Member States in enhancing their surveillance and IT systems in a cohesive manner and ensure data quality, system interoperability and comparability of data outputs.
- Clear and concise case definitions are essential to establish a surveillance system and allow for appropriate interpretation of data. Such definitions should ideally be harmonised at national as well at international level to allow for data compatibility.
- For countries to be able to link data and develop automated systems it is imperative that capacities need to be strengthened towards the development of high-end IT infrastructures and focus placed on increasing HR related to IT including data engineers and analysts to ensure the upkeep of dynamic surveillance systems.

The future implementation of the PD system in state hospitals would assist in improving data standardisation and subsequent quality for a more robust syndromic surveillance system. The this effect several meetings were held with the hospital IT department to ensure that the necessary data for public health surveillance is captured in a standardised manner for good quality outputs and analysis.

Through the implementation of MIDISS Malta aims to close several gaps with regards to public health surveillance by creating the necessary IT infrastructure needed to link, process and visualise data from various stakeholders in a secure manner.

Malta is also planning to further enhance the GI surveillance by incorporating into the system the Outbreak detection tool developed and piloted as part of the outputs of WP2 of the Joint Action in which Malta was an active participant. Add here; could also include planned next steps in the future.

2.3.6. Core messages

The core messages from the Malta pilot study are:

- Importance of having a robust legal basis to allow for secondary processing of public health data as well as data sharing agreements with hospitals and other relevant stakeholders to ensure cooperation for sharing of data in a secure manner.
- Importance of interdisciplinary collaboration between hospitals and healthcare institutions, Public Health, IT, One Health stakeholders as well as data protection and legal experts when developing IT systems to allow for interoperability of systems and automated real-time public health surveillance which is necessary for preparedness.
- Need for established surveillance standards and models to assist Member States in enhancing their surveillance and IT systems in a cohesive manner and ensure data quality, system interoperability and comparability of data outputs.

2.4 Pilot in Slovenia

2.4.1. Background & objectives

The National Institute of Public Health (in Slovenian: Nacionalni inštitut za javno zdravje - NIJZ), in collaboration with the University Medical Centre Ljubljana (in Slovenian: Univerzitetni klinični center Ljubljana - UKCL) and the National Laboratory for Health, Environment and Food (in Slovenian: Nacionalni laboratorij za zdravje, okolje in hrano – NLZOH), conducted a pilot project to support the transition from the current national paper-based system to an electronic health record (EHR)-based national surveillance of severe acute respiratory infections (SARI) in Slovenia.

National paper-based SARI infection surveillance in Slovenia has been in operation since 2020. As it was developed in response to the COVID-19 pandemic, only the incidence of SARI cases caused by SARS-CoV-2 infection has been monitored. Although effective, the surveillance system relied on manual, paper-based weekly reporting from hospitals, which limited both timeliness and operational efficiency, also because in addition to clinical work, it required extra time for healthcare workers to manually collect and report SARI surveillance data to the NIJZ.

The planned EHR-based SARI surveillance system will deliver more accurate and timely data based on the secondary use of appropriately structured electronic health care data submitted to the Central Registry of Patient Data (in Slovenian: Centralni register podatkov o pacientih – CRPP) at the NIJZ from all Slovenian acute care hospitals and microbiology laboratories. From the CRPP, the SARI data will be harvested for secondary use, in particular SARI surveillance, to the Communicable Diseases Databases (CDD) at the NIJZ.

Primary objectives of the planned national EHR-based SARI surveillance will be to monitor, in near real-time:

- the incidence of SARI hospital admissions,
- the incidence of SARI admissions to ICUs and
- in-hospital SARI mortality,

All of these overall, by age group, and by pathogens, in particular: SARS-CoV-2, influenza viruses, and RSV.

The pilot encompassed:

- the identification of the above listed EHR-based SARI surveillance primary objectives,
- the identification of respective key data elements needed,
- mapping of respective data elements in appropriately structured format in the UKCL and NLZOH information technology (IT) systems,
- plans for the adaptation of respective information recording in hospital and microbiology laboratories IT systems in appropriately structured and standardised format,
- development of and/or plans for the development of respective IT solutions for appropriately structured data collection in hospitals and microbiology laboratories IT systems, and drafting national EHR-based SARI surveillance protocol.

2.4.2. Outcome/delivered product

The pilot project resulted in the first draft of a national EHR-based SARI surveillance protocol which will serve as the foundation for the implementation of the future national EHR-based SARI surveillance system, aiming for real-time, accurate, and integrated national SARI surveillance in Slovenia. This draft protocol includes:

- defined SARI surveillance objectives listed above,
- case definitions for SARI hospital admission, SARI admission to ICUs, in-hospital SARI death, SARI caused by SARS-CoV-2 infection, SARI caused by influenza virus infection, and SARI caused by RSV infection given below,

- structured hospital and microbiology laboratories data models with coding,
- description of planned data flow from data providers to the NIJZ (Figure 3.4.1).

Additional key achievements of our pilot include:

- mapping of required appropriately structured data availability in UKCL's and NLZOH IT systems,
- development of proposal for IT solutions and data transfer from healthcare providers to the CRPP,
- development of an IT solution enabling near real-time hospital admission/discharge data receipt at the CRPP and for the transfer of such data from one of the three UMCL IT systems (Clinical) to CRPP,
- review of legal framework and preparation of a proposal for currently enacted legal basis for SARI surveillance.

2.4.2.1. Definitions

A hospitalised patient is defined as someone admitted for a defined period of time, whether this is calculated as the number of hours (e.g., >24 hours) or days (e.g., an admission of >1 day).

SARI is defined as a patient hospitalised (for at least 24 hours) and has one of the following International Classification of Diseases 10th Revision (ICD-10) codes recorded as admission and/or as discharge diagnosis:

J09	Influenza due to identified zoonotic or pandemic influenza virus
J10	Influenza due to identified seasonal influenza virus
J10.0	Influenza with pneumonia, seasonal influenza virus identified
J10.1	Influenza with other respiratory manifestations, seasonal influenza virus identified
J10.8	Influenza with other manifestations, seasonal influenza virus identified
J11	Influenza, virus not identified
J11.0	Influenza with pneumonia, virus not identified
J11.1	Influenza with other respiratory manifestations, virus not identified
J11.8	Influenza with other manifestations, virus not identified
J12	Viral pneumonia, not elsewhere classified
J12.0	Adenoviral pneumonia
J12.1	Respiratory syncytial virus pneumonia
J12.2	Parainfluenza virus pneumonia
J12.3	Human metapneumovirus pneumonia
J12.8	Other viral pneumonia
J12.9	Viral pneumonia, unspecified
J13	Pneumonia due to <i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>
J14	Pneumonia due to <i>Haemophilus influenzae</i>
J15	Bacterial pneumonia, not elsewhere classified
J15.0	Pneumonia due to <i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>
J15.1	Pneumonia due to Pseudomonas
J15.2	Pneumonia due to staphylococcus
J15.3	Pneumonia due to streptococcus, group B
J15.4	Pneumonia due to other streptococci
J15.5	Pneumonia due to <i>Escherichia coli</i>
J15.6	Pneumonia due to other Gram-negative bacteria
J15.7	Pneumonia due to <i>Mycoplasma pneumoniae</i>
J15.8	Other bacterial pneumonia
J15.9	Bacterial pneumonia, unspecified

J16	Pneumonia due to other infectious organisms, not elsewhere classified
J16.0	Chlamydial pneumonia
J16.8	Pneumonia due to other specified infectious organisms
J17	Pneumonia in diseases classified elsewhere
J17.0	Pneumonia in bacterial diseases classified elsewhere
J17.1	Pneumonia in viral diseases classified elsewhere
J17.2	Pneumonia in mycoses
J17.3	Pneumonia in parasitic diseases
J17.8	Pneumonia in other diseases classified elsewhere
J18	Pneumonia, organism unspecified
J18.0	Bronchopneumonia, unspecified
J18.1	Lobar pneumonia, unspecified
J18.2	Hypostatic pneumonia, unspecified
J18.8	Other pneumonia, organism unspecified
J18.9	Pneumonia, unspecified
J20	Acute bronchitis
J20.0	Acute bronchitis due to <i>Mycoplasma pneumoniae</i>
J20.1	Acute bronchitis due to <i>Haemophilus influenzae</i>
J20.2	Acute bronchitis due to streptococcus
J20.3	Acute bronchitis due to coxsackievirus
J20.4	Acute bronchitis due to parainfluenza virus
J20.5	Acute bronchitis due to respiratory syncytial virus
J20.6	Acute bronchitis due to rhinovirus
J20.7	Acute bronchitis due to echovirus
J20.8	Acute bronchitis due to other specified organisms
J20.9	Acute bronchitis, unspecified
J21	Acute bronchiolitis
J21.0	Acute bronchiolitis due to respiratory syncytial virus
J21.1	Acute bronchiolitis due to human metapneumovirus
J21.8	Acute bronchiolitis due to other specified organisms
J21.9	Acute bronchiolitis, unspecified
J22	Unspecified acute lower respiratory infection
A37	Whooping cough
A37.0	Whooping cough due to <i>Bordetella pertussis</i>
A37.1	Whooping cough due to <i>Bordetella parapertussis</i>
A48.1	Legionnaires disease
B97.2	Coronavirus as the cause of diseases classified to other chapters
B97.4	Respiratory syncytial virus as the cause of diseases classified to other chapters
B34.2	Coronavirus infection, unspecified site

SARI admitted to ICU is defined as a SARI case admitted to an ICU during the hospitalisation episode. An ICU is defined as “an organised system for the provision of care to critically ill patients that provides intensive and specialised medical and nursing care, an enhanced capacity for monitoring, and multiple modalities of physiologic organ support to sustain life during a period of life-threatening organ system insufficiency”.

SARI in-hospital death is defined as a SARI case who died during the hospitalisation episode and has a respiratory infection (J09-J22, A37, A37.0, A37.1, A48.1, B97.2, B97.4, B34.2) listed as a cause of death on the death certificate.

SARI case data submitted from hospitals to CRPP are planned to be linked with microbiology testing data submitted to CRPP from hospitals and laboratories using EMŠO as a unique identifier.

Laboratory confirmed SARI caused by SARS-CoV-2 is defined if the following laboratory confirmation criteria are met:

- detection of viral nucleic acid of SARS-CoV-2 in a clinical specimen,
- identification of viral antigen of SARS-CoV-2 in a clinical specimen (if antigen tests are used in a healthcare organisation and performed by healthcare professionals trained for such testing),
- isolation of the virus of SARS-CoV-2 from a clinical specimen

In a respiratory sample collected between 10 days before at admission and 48 hours after hospital admission.

Laboratory confirmed SARI caused by influenza viruses is defined if the following laboratory confirmation criteria will be met:

- detection of viral nucleic acid of influenza virus in a clinical specimen,
- identification of viral antigen of influenza virus in a clinical specimen (if antigen tests are used in a healthcare organization and performed by healthcare professionals trained for such testing),
- isolation of the virus of influenza from a clinical specimen

In a respiratory sample collected between 10 days before at admission and 48 hours after hospital admission.

Laboratory confirmed SARI caused by RSV is defined if the following laboratory confirmation criteria will be met:

- detection of viral nucleic acid of RSV in a clinical specimen,
- identification of viral antigen of RSV in a clinical specimen (if antigen tests are used in a healthcare organisation and performed by healthcare professionals trained for such testing),
- isolation of the RSV from a clinical specimen

In a respiratory sample collected between 10 days before at admission and 48 hours after hospital admission.

A laboratory confirmed SARI caused by influenza virus case is in addition to the above definition also defined as a patient hospitalised (for at least 24 hours) and has one of the following ICD-10 codes recorded as admission diagnosis: J9, J10, J10.0, J10.1, J10.8. and

A laboratory confirmed SARI caused by RSV case is defined as a patient hospitalised (for at least 24 hours) and has one of the following ICD-10 codes recorded as admission diagnosis: J12.1, J20.5, J21.0, B97.4.

2.4.2.2. Description of data flow

The planned data flow for national EHR-based SARI surveillance system is consistent with the planned general EHR-based surveillance of all communicable diseases and will involve five different data models, sets of variables with respective coding:

- Data (variables) to be transferred to CRPP from hospitals,
- Data (variables) to be transferred to CRPP from microbiology laboratories,
- Data (variables) about deaths submitted to the CRPP by hospitals,
- Data (variables) harvested from Central Population Registry (in Slovenian: Centralni register prebivalcev – CRP),

- Data (variables) harvested from CRPP into the CDD.

This planned data flow for national EHR-based SARI surveillance is shown on Figure 3.4.2.1.

Figure 2.4.2.2. Planned national EHR-based SARI surveillance data flow

2.4.2.3. SARI surveillance legal basis

We reviewed the legal framework for SARI surveillance during the COVID-19 pandemic, that expired by the end of 2024 and prepared a proposal for a current legal basis for SARI surveillance for the Ministry of Health and the Parliament. The respective current legal basis for EPISARI is the article 13 of the “Act on additional intervention measures to ensure accessibility in healthcare”, which was adopted by the Parliament in December 2024. The text of the article 13 is as follows:

“(1) For the purpose of epidemiological monitoring of hospitalizations due to acute respiratory infections and acute respiratory infections in which infection with the SARS-CoV-2 virus or influenza viruses or respiratory syncytial virus (hereinafter referred to as: RSV) was confirmed, hospitals shall submit to the National Institute of Public Health (hereinafter referred to as: NIJZ) on a weekly basis the number of persons admitted to hospitals due to acute respiratory infections and the EMŠO of the following persons:

1. persons admitted to hospital due to acute respiratory infection in which infection with the SARS-CoV-2 virus or influenza viruses or RSV was confirmed,
2. persons admitted to intensive care units due to acute respiratory infection in which infection with the SARS-CoV-2 virus or influenza viruses or RSV was confirmed and
3. persons who died in hospital due to acute respiratory infection in which the cause of death was infection with the SARS-CoV-2 virus or influenza viruses or RSV.

(2) The provisions of the Health Care Databases Act (in Slovenian.: Zakon o zbirkah podatkov s področja zdravstvenega varstva (ZZPPZ) shall apply to the collection, processing and transmission of personal data referred to in the previous paragraph, their protection, recording, application of methodological principles and supervision, as they apply to the NIJZ 48 Communicable Diseases Database (CDD) from Annex 1 of the ZZPPZ. Under the same conditions, the collection shall also be linked to other collections managed in accordance with

the ZZPPZ for the performance of tasks referred to in Article 23a of the Health Care Act (in Slovenian: Zakon o zdravstveni dejavnosti – ZZDej).

(3) The measure referred to in this Article shall be valid from 1 January 2025 to 31 December 2025. If the expert opinion of the NIJZ shows that acute respiratory infections and respiratory infections in which infection with the SARS-CoV-2 virus, influenza viruses or RSV has been confirmed are still occurring continuously, the Government may extend the measure referred to in this Article by decision no more than twice, each time for a maximum of six months. The decision to extend the measure shall be published in the Official Gazette of the Republic of Slovenia.”

2.4.3. Impact

The pilot contributed to strengthening communicable diseases surveillance in Slovenia by laying the groundwork for a more efficient, EHR-based, and near real-time SARI surveillance system. It demonstrated the feasibility of integrating EHR data into national SARI surveillance and helped us to identify key legal, technical, and organisational requirements for its implementation.

By replacing the current paper-based national SARI surveillance system, the future EHR-based SARI surveillance approach will:

- improve data accuracy and timeliness,
- reduce the reporting burden for hospitals and microbiology laboratories,
- lessen data processing workload at NIJZ, and
- support faster and more informed public health responses not only for SARS-CoV-2 infections but also for influenza and RSV infections.

The pilot fostered collaboration across key stakeholders, hospitals, microbiology laboratories, NIJZ and the Ministry of Health. It also resulted in preparing the current legal basis for SARI surveillance according to which we started to collect data on SARI admissions to hospitals and ICUs together with data about the other pathogens of public health importance causing SARI, such as influenza and RSV in addition to SARI cases caused by SARS-CoV-2 infections.

We also managed to obtain current legal basis for national SARI surveillance, the article 13 of the “Act on additional intervention measures to ensure accessibility in healthcare”, which was adopted in December 2024 and is expected to be enacted until the end of 2026. This will contribute to shaping future legislation, reinforcing the digital transformation of public health surveillance in Slovenia.

2.4.4. Lessons learned

The pilot project provided valuable insights into both the opportunities and challenges associated with transitioning to an EHR-based national SARI surveillance system.

One of the key successes was the collaboration between NIJZ, UKCL, NLZOH and the Ministry of Health, which facilitated progress in both technical planning and alignment with legal and public health frameworks. Early identification of core data elements and mapping of data availability across existing IT systems in the UKCL, NLZOH and CRPP proved to be a sound approach, allowing for the development of realistic data models and functional design proposals. Furthermore, the pilot successfully demonstrated that real-time data transfer to the CRPP is technically feasible, setting the stage for future scalability.

However, several challenges emerged. The lack of standardisation and the fragmented nature of hospital IT systems will make it difficult to ensure uniform data extraction and processing across institutions. Resource limitations—both financial and technical—also restricted the full implementation and testing of proposed IT solutions during the pilot period.

2.4.5. Recommendations

Based on the pilot findings, several key recommendations have been identified to support the successful implementation of a national EHR-based SARI surveillance system. Establishing a permanent legal framework for EHR-based surveillance of communicable diseases, including SARI, is essential to ensure continuity and scalability beyond the current temporary legal provisions. This legal foundation should enable secure access to, and integration of relevant data sources across healthcare institutions.

Standardising and harmonising hospital information systems remains critical to enable consistent data collection, improve interoperability, and ensure reliable capture and transmission of essential variables. Dedicated technical and financial resources must be secured to support ongoing development and implementation of IT solutions and to build institutional capacity for data management and surveillance.

Moving forward, we will continue activities to digitalise the national SARI surveillance system within the framework of the EU4Health-funded project “Digitalisation of the national communicable diseases surveillance system in Slovenia (NSS-SI).” This initiative will expand and enhance the real-time data transfer solutions piloted at the University Medical Centre Ljubljana and facilitate their rollout across other healthcare settings, ensuring scalability and improved system performance.

The draft EHR-based SARI surveillance protocol will be regularly updated to reflect evolving legal, technical, and stakeholder requirements. Sustained collaboration with hospitals, laboratories, government agencies, and other stakeholders will be crucial for refining the system and achieving successful national implementation.

The upcoming Digitalization of Health Care Act, expected to be adopted by the end of 2026, is anticipated to further support these efforts by addressing long-term data governance, integration, and surveillance needs. Currently the relevant national legislation is the Health Care Databases Act (in Slovenian: Zakon o zbirkah podatkov s področja zdravstvenega varstva, ZZPPZ).

2.4.6. Core messages

Collaboration and coordination among NIJZ, hospitals, microbiology laboratories and the Ministry of Health is key to develop and implement EHR-based SARI surveillance system. Stakeholders should recognize that the success of this initiative depends on strong collaboration across healthcare institutions and standardised and interoperable data systems.

Appropriate national and international legal framework is necessary to implement EHR-based SARI surveillance system and ensure secure and efficient data sharing.

The transition from national paper-based to an EHR-based surveillance system for SARI will represent a major advancement in Slovenia’s communicable diseases surveillance capabilities. This new digitalised SARI surveillance system will provide near real-time, high-quality data on hospitalisations, ICUs admissions, and mortality associated with key respiratory pathogens, including SARS-CoV-2, influenza, and RSV. By replacing the current paper-based reporting, it will significantly improve the timeliness, accuracy, and completeness of surveillance data.

Ultimately, the EHR-based SARI surveillance system will reduce administrative burdens on healthcare providers while enabling more informed, evidence-based public health decision-making. This modernisation effort will enhance Slovenia's capacity to respond promptly and effectively to respiratory infectious disease threats, supporting national health security and aligning with broader European public health objectives.

3. Pilot experience, evaluation and recommendations from Task 3.2 – Integrate clinical information on hospitalised patients with microbiological data (typing and microbial resistance), in Member States using nation-wide register-based public health surveillance

The focus of this task is the integration of clinical information describing the course of illness with microbiological data from laboratories at the national level. In several countries the foundation for this integration is the national infectious disease register, which receives notifications of positive microbiological test results from clinical laboratories. This data can be linked with clinical information from healthcare services using a unique personal identifier. Reliable and timely incidence of hospitalised persons can be used to characterise disease waves and disease burden, and with vaccination information, to monitor vaccine effectiveness.

Of the four countries piloting, **Norway** and **Finland** both have been able to link hospitalisation data with microbiological data on a national level with regular time-intervals, and practically without delay, during the COVID-19 pandemic. In their pilots, both countries worked on technical and legal improvements for SARI surveillance as routine surveillance. In the Norwegian pilot, the concept for a new system was described, including identifying the legal basis for such surveillance. In Finland, data flow existed but the legal framework, algorithms and definitions, as well as improvement in the diversity of data, were needed. For both Norway and Finland, the work continues in EU4Health funded NorSurv and FinSurveillance projects.

The aim of the **Polish** pilot was to explore the potential for strengthening the national surveillance by analysing the structure and availability of existing data sources across the healthcare system, types of variables recorded, and to identify potential linkage points to understand where integration might be possible. The pilot provided insights on a range of systemic, legal, technical, and organisational barriers that limit the integration of routinely collected data for public health surveillance. These findings were synthesized and categorised into six thematic areas: environment, management, processes, technology, manpower and data. Polish work will continue in the EU4Health funded project “Implementation of IT and training solutions for All Hazards Early Warning – PNEWRS”.

In **Italy**, antimicrobial resistance (AMR) surveillance involves approximately 150 laboratories and covers more than 50% of hospital days nationally. Labs report AMR data to the Istituto Superiore di Sanità (ISS). However, microbiological datasets lack accompanying clinical information. In Italy there are 21 Regions/Autonomous provinces that are autonomous for health matters and there is no national automatic network/system for laboratory or clinical data. A major barrier encountered was the absence of a legal framework that permits the linking of pseudonymised datasets collected for different purposes across institutions. The pilot led to the drafting of a technical-operational protocol to link clinical data from the GiViTI network of Intensive Care Units with microbiological data from ARS Toscana (Regional Health Agency in Tuscany). The pilot outlined the legal and technical frameworks necessary for secure data linkage, such as harmonisation of pseudonymisation techniques across institutions to facilitate interoperability, and development of national legislation. Work continues in the EU4Health funded project “StePs foRward foR digital and real time surVeillance of Infectious DiseasEs IN ITaly”(PROVIDENT).

3.1 Pilot in Finland

3.1.1. Background & objectives

Before the COVID-19 pandemic, the existing Care Register for Health Care (HILMO) was updated only once a year. However, during the pandemic, the system was improved so that discharge diagnoses are now reported practically in real time. This advancement significantly enhanced the potential for infectious disease surveillance.

The aim of this pilot was to enable the reporting of severe hospitalised cases of influenza, RSV (respiratory syncytial virus), and COVID-19 in Finland using only register-based data. The objective was to explore how to link the Care Register for Health Care (HILMO) with laboratory notifications in the National Infectious Diseases Register (NIDR), and to determine how to define cases in an age-specific, timely, and consistent way to obtain accurate information on hospitalisations. The pilot also aimed to expand the range of laboratory-based data available, including pathogen typing and antimicrobial resistance (AMR) information.

Although most of the necessary data are already included in national registers, there are legal, technical, and organisational obstacles regarding the continuous linking of these datasets that needed to be identified and addressed. To initiate legislative changes, we first began discussions with the legal experts at the Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL), and subsequently engaged with the legal advisors at the Ministry of Social Affairs and Health, as well as with the Office of the Data Protection Ombudsman.

3.1.2. Outcome/delivered product

- For piloting, as well as for other ad hoc studies, data can be obtained from the registers with specific one-time permit, but to keep the registers linked permanently requires major adjustments in legislations in Finland. In this project, the changes needed in legislations were mapped, analysed, justified, and delivered to the Ministry of Social Affairs and Health to be taken into account in the current updating of Communicable Diseases Act.
- Cases were defined with specific and unspecific ICD-10 coding lists, episode definitions etc. from 2016 onwards, which gave insight in coding practises and allowed for well-defined and tested surveillance definitions and algorithms for severe Covid-19, Influenza and RSV for improved usability in the long run.
- Data on microbiological tests was identified, and testing protocols analysed.
- The details on definitions and algorithms are published in an article, work ongoing during summer-autumn 2025.

3.1.3. Impact

One aim of updating the Communicable Diseases Act is for the legislation to allow integrating data sources in a continuous manner. In addition, as the Act was analysed, it was obvious that other **legislative changes** would be needed as well (for example allowing to collect individual contact tracing data to the central national level) even though that was not primarily needed for this Joint Action.

In our UNITED4Surveillance pilot, which was only considering respiratory infections, we also **aimed to pilot how to proceed to other severe infections**. This is continued in the EU4Health funded Direct Grant project FinSurveillance.

In UNITED4Surveillance we have analysed how severe respiratory infections are coded in Finland, and how laboratory diagnostics are carried out. **With these we could define the electronic surveillance targets and link the registers for better surveillance data** (COVID-19, Influenza, RSV). All hospitalisations due to diagnosis

relevant for respiratory infection symptom ICD-10 codes were linked with the National Infectious Diseases Register laboratory notifications and visualized in a THL internal web-based “ShinyApp” application, allowing different case definitions to be tested.

The definitions and algorithms allow data on severe hospitalised respiratory infections of COVID-19, Influenza and RSV to be collected in a timely and resource saving manner. The implications of the efforts in this WP are that reliable data on severe hospitalised respiratory infections can also be delivered to the EU level surveillance systems from Finland.

The **work with different case definitions has been and will be utilised for example in COVID-19 vaccine effectiveness studies** (1), (2). Furthermore, COVID-19 hospitalisation data was an endpoint in Number Needed to Vaccinate analyses carried out during spring 2024 (3) and 2025 (4), to form the national COVID-19 vaccination policy for autumn 2024 and 2025.

Defined influenza hospitalisations have been used in national influenza surveillance (5) and for example in European Medicine Agency funded brand-specific vaccination effectiveness study carried out as a joint venture with Danish and Swedish national organisations in 2025 (6).

(1) Poukka E, et al. Relative effectiveness of bivalent boosters against severe COVID-19 outcomes among people aged ≥ 65 years in Finland, September 2022 to August 2023. *Euro Surveill.* 2024;29(37):pii=2300587.

(2) Poukka E, et al. COVID-19 Vaccine Effectiveness Among Adolescents. *Pediatrics* 2024;153(2):e2023062520.

(3) Who needs the Covid-19 vaccination during autumn 2024?, NNV calculations based on national hospitalisation and mortality data: https://www.julkari.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/149069/URN_ISBN_978-952-408-318-8.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y

(4) Who needs the Covid-19 vaccination during autumn 2025?

https://www.julkari.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/151549/TY%C3%962025_025_Kuka%20tarvitsee%20koronaro%20kotuksen%20syksyll%C3%A4%202025_s.pdf?sequence=9&isAllowed=y

(5) Baum U, et al. Influenza Epidemiology in Finland During and After the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Influenza and Other Respiratory Viruses*. DOI: 10.1111/irv.70131. Accepted 6.6.2025

(6) European Medicine Agency funded study on brand-specific influenza vaccine in 3 Nordic countries:

<https://catalogues.ema.europa.eu/system/files/2025-02/Brand-specific%20IVE%20in%20Nordic%20settings.pdf>

3.1.4. Lessons learned

Even though EU legislation exists, a significant workload remains to obtain a mandate to permanently link the registers for surveillance purposes. To secure this mandate, **extensive stakeholder consultation** has been beneficial -- for example, infectious disease clinicians, lawyers at different levels of health care, and the Data Protection Ombudsman.

Presently, only positive microbiological test results are notified to the National Infectious Diseases Register. However, further information could have been incorporated into algorithms if **test data** (including also negative results) had been available. In the EU4Health funded Direct Grant project FinSurveillance, one task is to add data on all microbiological tests (positive and negative results) to the surveillance platform.

There was a plan to send clinical information, i.e. hospitalisation data, back to THL's own laboratories in the Microbiology unit for it to be taken into consideration while deciding which strains are typed further, but that was not possible as laboratory information system **renovation in THL (LIMSSI) is finishing only in late 2025**.

During the work it became obvious that some hospitals were involved in **point-of-care** treatment – i.e. bedside tests were used, data entered to the patient file, but no laboratory notification of the microbiological results was sent to National Infectious Diseases Register. Case definitions requiring laboratory confirmation, as a golden standard, turned out to be problematic.

When integrating clinical information on hospitalised patients with microbiological data, clear case definitions are essential. Several algorithms can be used to define a case—for example, a COVID-19 hospitalisation:

- 1) A specific ICD-10 code without requiring separate microbiological confirmation
- 2) A specific ICD-10 code with required microbiological confirmation
- 3) A non-specific ICD-10 code, such as a general respiratory symptom code, combined with microbiological confirmation found in a separate register.

The sensitivity and specificity of these different algorithms were evaluated to determine which one would form the basis for the data submitted, for example, to ECDC. A scientific article titled "Defining Severe Acute Respiratory Infection (SARI) Hospitalisations in Finland: Evaluation of Case Definitions for Register-Based Surveillance, 2021–2024" is also being written on the results.

3.1.5. Recommendations

There was a plan to send hospitalisation data back to THLs laboratories, so that it could be considered in decisions regarding typing and other related actions. However, this has not yet been possible, as the renovation of the laboratory information system at THL is still ongoing. Nevertheless, the goal of transferring clinical information to central laboratories remains important.

The extent of bedside testing used by the wellbeing services counties (regions) should be assessed, and solutions should be sought to address the lack of notifications related to these tests. All tests performed—including negative results—should be collected at the national level with personal identifiers.

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) data should be included in laboratory notifications in NIDR so that it can be also linked with hospitalisation data to enable analysis of AMR in infections that result in hospitalisation.

As the Communicable Diseases Act is being updated, the list of infections notifiable by laboratories should be revised to reflect evolving surveillance needs, and thus raising requirements for surveillance across EU Member States. In addition, as register linking with unique patient identifier is possible, more data sources should be used in public health surveillance—for example, the national income register (to identify workplace or occupational exposures to microbiological risks) and records of medication purchases (to help define risk groups). Interoperability of these systems is vital.

3.1.6. Core messages

For surveillance, digital definitions and algorithms are important for automating the processes.

Surveying severe infections by integrating data from national registers is timely, robust, less resource consuming, and does not require manual data entry when compared to separate physician notifications.

3.2 Pilot in Italy

3.2.1. Background & objectives

In Italy, antimicrobial resistance (AMR) surveillance is coordinated through the AR-ISS system, which involves approximately 150 laboratories. These labs contribute data to the Istituto Superiore di Sanità (ISS), and subsequently to the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) via the EARS-Net system. Surveillance covers more than 50% of hospital days nationally. Data is collected in a decentralized manner by regional authorities, allowing for improved utility at the local level that is sent yearly using email or file transfer system. However, the microbiological datasets largely lack accompanying clinical information. In Italy there are 21 Regions/Autonomous provinces that are autonomous for health matters and at the present there is no national automatic network/system for laboratory or clinical data. Furthermore, data linkage between such kinds of sources is not considered in any national law also for public health purposes. We attempted to establish a data linkage in a Region where a strong network on AMR is present and there is also a network of Intensive care units that collect clinical data. In Tuscany, a region with a population of 3.7 million, the 'SMART' network, coordinated by the Regional Health Agency (ARS), collects microbiological data from Laboratory Information Systems. ARS is responsible for collecting, analyzing, and disseminating health data in Tuscany to inform public health policies. ARS is responsible for collecting, analyzing, and disseminating health data in Tuscany to inform public health policies. The Tuscany Regional Health Agency (ARS), established by Regional Law No. 71 of September 30, 1998, serves as a technical agency providing scientific support and consultancy to both the Regional Council and the Regional Executive. In its role, ARS is responsible for collecting, analyzing, and disseminating all health data to inform public health policies and improve healthcare services.

The SMART network collects microbiological data from Laboratory Information Systems in 95% of regional hospitals. All data available at ARS is pseudo-anonymized at the regional level with a unique personal code that allows the same individual to be identified over time and in different databases, including the 'SMART' network.

Separately, the Italian Group for the Evaluation of Interventions in Intensive Care Units (GiViTI) network, held by the Mario Negri Pharmacological Research Institute IRCCS (IRFMN), collects clinical data from Intensive Care Units (ICUs) with the PROSAFE project, a non-profit, observational, multicentered study aimed at implementing a quality monitoring program for ICUs participating in the program. Since 2013, an agreement has been in place between the IRFMN and the Tuscany Region, which involves the epidemiological analysis of data collected using the PROSAFE software. Through this analysis, IRFMN generates indicators that provide a detailed view of the strengths and areas for improvement of the departments participating in the program. Because the GPDR in Italy does not permit a data linkage between AMR data e clinical data without a legal act that establish the need of this, several meetings were conducted with the data protection officer of the two Regions to find a possible solution for a regional data linkage. Because a solution was not funded, this pilot aims to test the feasibility of linking these two datasets using a regional pseudonymized patient identifier. A secondary objective is to study the feasibility of using national anonymized codes (CUNI/CUNA) for similar linkages at the national level.

3.2.2. Outcome/delivered product

The pilot led to the drafting of a technical-operational protocol to link clinical data from the GiViTI network with microbiological data from ARS Toscana. The pilot also outlined the legal and technical frameworks necessary for secure data linkage. The actual implementation of the protocol is subject to GiViTI's possibility to collect the medical record number. This involved engagement with stakeholders and regulatory

authorities (regional DPO), ensuring compliance with data protection regulations in case a future legal act. The technical feasibility of the protocol's implementation has been verified.

3.2.3. Impact

The possibility of strengthening AMR surveillance in Tuscany by enabling the integration of microbiological results with clinical data for ICU patients paves the way for new epidemiological analyses, including risk factor identification, infection outcome monitoring, and benchmarking of ICU performance. This integration provides a more comprehensive view of patient care and antimicrobial resistance trends, helping to inform regional health policy.

3.2.4. Lessons learned

This initiative in Italy represents a pioneering example of structured collaboration between IT specialists, data protection experts at both regional and national levels, and a research institute. The objective was to explore viable pathways for enhancing antimicrobial resistance (AMR) surveillance by enabling the linkage of administrative and clinical databases.

A major barrier encountered was the absence of a legal framework that permits the linking of pseudonymized datasets collected for different purposes across institutions. To strengthen patient privacy protections, the personal identifier used in PROSAFE is a study-specific code and does not correspond to the unique regional or ministerial identifier. Currently, legislative limits exist on the possibility of integrating data from a clinical study with the unique regional identifier, both at the level of the hospital entity (Data Controller) and at the level of the study-coordinating centre (IRFMN). A possible solution is based on connecting the data of interest on the medical record number.

Operational challenges included differences in pseudonymization methods. Effective stakeholder coordination was essential, and future projects should plan for sustained legal and IT collaboration from the beginning

3.2.5. Recommendations

It is recommended to develop national legislation that provides a legal basis for surveillance-related data linkages, with defined roles and responsibilities for all Data Controllers and Processors. Furthermore, harmonization of pseudonymization techniques across institutions would facilitate broader interoperability. The Tuscany pilot should be used as a model for similar projects in other regions, tailored to local legal and technical environments.

3.2.6. Core messages

Integrated surveillance combining clinical and microbiological data is technically feasible but currently restricted by regulatory and operational limitations. Tuscany has demonstrated a promising model, but broader implementation will require legal reform and standardization. Building upon the existing strengths of SMART and GiViTI, Italy can significantly enhance its national AMR surveillance system.

3.3 Pilot in Norway

3.3.1. Background & objectives

The purpose of this pilot was to plan and design a concept for a surveillance system of hospital admissions with laboratory confirmed respiratory tract infections using data from pre-existing sources. The system should routinely provide surveillance data in a peacetime setting, with the capability to scale up in case of a crisis. We described the basic principles for such a system with emphasis on some general legal and privacy aspects, infrastructure deficits, necessary data sources, and possibilities and hurdles for receiving data. The pilot was limited to investigating the basic framework for a surveillance system. Further assessment of the impact on personal data protection needs to be carried out. The testing, implementation and operation of the system was not within the scope of the planned pilot, but it hopefully did form a clear recommendation for follow-up. Production of a Severe Acute and Respiratory Illness (SARI) surveillance protocol describing surveillance indicators and defining case definitions was not within the scope of this pilot, nor was it validating or evaluating a SARI surveillance system and its indicators.

3.3.2. Outcome/delivered product

The recommendations from this pilot laid the groundwork for the NORSURV Direct Grant (CP-g-23-01¹) to make improvements to the Norwegian surveillance systems for infectious diseases.

The pilot report, within Work Package 3 Hospital Surveillance, focused on the necessity for developing a SARI surveillance system in Norway that integrates clinical and laboratory information for routine surveillance in peacetime. Its basis was drawn from the learnings achieved from building a temporary SARI surveillance system in the COVID-19 preparedness register (Beredt C19) in a time of crisis.

3.3.3. Impact

The pilot report WP3: Surveillance of hospital admissions with respiratory tract infections in Norway - possibilities and hurdles² will be of most value when viewed in light of other reports concerning SARI and registry-based surveillance in Norway, based on our lessons learned throughout the COVID-19 pandemic, e.g.:

- Protocol for establishment of a registry-based national SARI surveillance system in Norway (October, 2021)
- Protocol for Severe Acute Respiratory Infections (SARI) surveillance in Norway (01.07.2022)³
- EHR-SARI evaluation protocol; Evaluation of SARI surveillance – Norway (05.05.2023)³
- General description of the Norwegian SARI surveillance system as of 2023-W20 (17.02.2023)³
- EHR-based SARI surveillance; Annual report; NORWAY (28.04.2024)³
- EHR-based SARI surveillance; Annual report; NORWAY (06.02.2024)³

¹ EU4H-2023-DGA-MS-IBA-01 — Direct grants to Member States' authorities: improving and strengthening national surveillance systems (Regulation 2022/2371 of the European Parliament and of the Council on serious cross-border threats to health)

² Norwegian Institute of Public Health, O'Donnell, R. P., & Paulsen, T. H. (2024). Pilot report WP3: Surveillance of hospital admissions with respiratory tract infections in Norway - possibilities and hurdles (final version). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14330172>

³ This activity was partially supported by the projects "Vaccine Effectiveness, Burden and Impact Studies (VEBIS) of COVID-19 and Influenza", funded by the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control through service contracts with Epiconcept (ECD.13350 and ECD.15029, implementing framework contract ECDC/2021/016), and "Design and implementation of multinational surveillance systems using routinely collected electronic health records in EU/EEA", funded by the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control through service contracts with the E-Sure Consortium (ECD.13629, ECD.14898, and ECD.16380, implementing framework contract ECDC/2022/003).

- Registry-Based Surveillance of Severe Acute Respiratory Infections in Norway During 2021-2024. Seppälä E et al. Influenza Other Respir Viruses. 2025 Feb;19(2):e70080. doi: 10.1111/irv.70080. PMID: 39950571; PMCID: PMC11826439.
- Hospitalisations for COVID-19 - a comparison of different data sources. Whittaker R et al. Tidsskr Nor Lægeforen. 2020 Dec 14;140(18). English, Norwegian. doi: 10.4045/tidsskr.20.0759
- A comparison of two registry-based systems for the surveillance of persons hospitalised with COVID-19 in Norway, February 2020 to May 2022. Whittaker R et al. Euro Surveill. 2023;28(33):pii=2200888.
- Surveillance of severe acute respiratory infections associated with SARS-CoV-2, influenza virus and RSV using ICD-10 codes: a case definition accuracy study across six European countries, 2021-2023. Ruiz MAS et al. Work ongoing³
- Changed epidemiology of influenza and RSV hospitalizations after the emergence of SARS-CoV-2 in Norway, 2017 - 2024. Bøås H et al. Ann Epidemiol. 2025 Jun 19:S1047-2797(25)00132-2. doi: 10.1016/j.annepidem.2025.06.010. Epub ahead of print. PMID: 40543765.
- Surveillance of hospitalisations with laboratory-confirmed respiratory infections using the national laboratory database, Norway, 2022-2024. Seppälä et al. Preprint available at <https://www.authorea.com/users/820406/articles/1220588-surveillance-of-hospitalisations-with-laboratory-confirmed-respiratory-infections-using-the-national-laboratory-database-norway-2022-2024>.

Not all of these documents are readily available online. Please contact corresponding author Trine Hessevik Paulsen (trinehessevik.paulsen@fhi) for access.

3.3.4. Lessons learned

Several aspects either facilitated the work of the pilot in realizing its objectives, or in other ways affected it, including:

- A working group formed of interdisciplinary composition, including legal expertise.
- Allowing for time at the beginning of the pilot, to reach a shared understanding among the group. Onboarding of new team members joining along the way, although temporarily slowing progress within the working group, was important for a shared understanding.
- There were several related yet independent processes which had consequences for and resulting from the pilot, an example was an assignment from the Ministry to describe a target vision for a comprehensive system for infection surveillance in Norway.
- Other initiatives within the NIPH to improve and facilitate the generation of evidence-based knowledge resulted in accelerated synergy effects from the pilot, although affecting the scope of the pilot.
- There were several unintended outcomes stimulated by pilot, for example the request and subsequent assessment clarifying the Communicable Diseases Control Act § 2-2, eighth paragraph.
- As surveillance is not mentioned specifically in the regulations of several of the central health registers then this became a challenge to justify the requirement for using data from those registers.
- It was very helpful to have support from both internal and external stakeholders whose strategy in this area aligned with that of the pilot. At the same time, this resulted in members of the piloting working group having to dedicate a lot of time to engage with and coordinate with other processes, which was the right approach so that our work became utilized.
- There were certain indirect benefits realized also, whereby it was determined that by using a different legal instrument with the purpose of producing anonymous statistics then surveillance could ensue during peace time and not just in a crisis.

- GDPR was not considered to be a major obstacle as national legislation supported the use of data for the purpose of the pilot.

3.3.5. Recommendations

1. Establish a clear and enduring legal basis for peacetime surveillance by updating relevant legislation and register-specific regulations to explicitly support continuous, non-crisis surveillance activities.
2. To ensure privacy compliance and secure data handling across all integrated registers, robust data minimization, access control and governance protocols must be implemented.
3. As the environment in which the pilot was delivered was one of fast-change as the COVID-19 pandemic drew to an end and the learnings from such a crisis were being rapidly applied, it is important to take a flexible approach to maximise synergies of the pilot with other parallel work.
4. It is important to demonstrate to involved stakeholders the rationale by which data is sought from the central health registers for the surveillance of SARI and what is the main function of interest for such a pilot. Therefore, demonstrating the criticality of obtaining access to these datasets for the purpose of SARI surveillance.

3.3.6. Core messages

When planning and designing a nation-wide register-based surveillance system, it is essential to begin by identifying the data sources you intend to use and prioritizing them based on their relevance and importance.

Next, clearly define the purpose of collecting this data—what you aim to achieve—and ensure that its use aligns with the applicable legal and regulatory frameworks as well as defined surveillance objectives. Finally, do not overlook the importance of secure data sharing. Given that data may come in various formats and structures, it is strongly recommended to implement robust data minimization practices to protect privacy and reduce risk.

3.4 Pilot in Poland

3.4.1. Background & objectives

In Poland, rotavirus infections have been under mandatory surveillance since 2005, accounting for over half of viral intestinal infections and resulting in 20,000-35,000 reported cases annually (except during the COVID-19 pandemic years). Around 90% of cases require hospitalisation.

Vaccination became recommended in 2007 (self-paid) and mandatory in 2021 for children born after 31 December 2020 (publicly funded). However, routine surveillance currently collects only general vaccination information. Since 2005, the epidemiological situation has been monitored based on aggregated data.

Rotavirus cases are not included in epidemiological surveillance at the EU level. As a result, no case definition has been introduced, and they are not reported to TESSy. Case-based data started to be collected at the central level in 2020, through the EpiBaza surveillance system. Data completeness in the EpiBaza system is limited - about 50% of cases are captured, and key hospitalisation dates are often missing. The optional introduction of the Vaccination e-Card in 2022 marked a transitional step toward digital vaccination records.

The objectives of the pilot were to define the framework for collaboration in sharing and integrating routinely collected data to strengthen the surveillance system in Poland.

The first phase involved identifying available systems, variables and data formats across those systems. Efforts to enhance data completeness and quality focused on supplementing information from other datasets, including:

1. hospitalisation details (e.g. duration, procedures),
2. clinically relevant information (e.g. comorbidities),
3. rotavirus vaccination status.

The project also planned to design secure functionalities for automated data transfer to reduce manual workload and expand existing systems (EpiBaza, ROE) to include additional variables.

Using rotavirus as a case example for the pilot improved our understanding of existing systems and their interoperability.

3.4.2. Outcome/delivered product

Three key outcomes were identified during the pilot and enhanced our understanding of how routinely collected data can be integrated into infectious disease surveillance:

1. Identification of relevant systems
2. Characterisation of data structures and variables within and across identified systems
3. Identification of key gaps

These findings highlighted the potential of existing data sources to support surveillance of rotavirus cases requiring hospitalization.

Several systems were identified as particularly relevant, including:

(Rotavirus) vaccination record

The Vaccination e-Card was introduced in March 2022. It allows doctors to register both mandatory and recommended vaccinations in electronic medical records. In 2007, rotavirus vaccination became recommended in Poland (fully paid by parents). Since 2021, rotavirus vaccination has been mandatory and free of charge for children born after 31 December 2020 (financed by the Ministry of Health). For rotavirus,

use of the e-Card is optional. Paper-based Immunization Cards are still accepted. Feeding the surveillance system with vaccination data can improve understanding of trends and disease severity among cases.

Hospital morbidity study

This dataset covers all hospitalisations in Poland, including patients without public insurance. The individual data are collected anonymously. It includes diagnoses, procedures, duration of hospitalisation, age, sex, and place of residence. It is the main national source of information on hospital morbidity. It can help assess completeness.

National health insurer data

The National Health Fund collects data from providers for financial claims. It covers about 90% of the population. Because reporting is required for payment, the records are usually complete.

Death certificate database

Statistics Poland collects death certificate data for each individual. These include date and place of death, cause of death (coded using ICD-10), and contributing factors. Basic demographic information is also recorded - such as age, sex, and place of residence.

Private laboratory database

This comes from the largest network of medical laboratories in Poland. It includes tests done for hospitals, clinics, and private providers. About one-third of the tests are ordered by hospitals. They might also provide total tests performed, which could help interpret trends in positive cases in relation to overall testing levels.

All three outcomes (identification of relevant systems, characterisation of data structures and variables within and across identified systems, identification of key gaps) were synthesized using an Ishikawa method. This method helped clarify the barriers that limit effective integration of health data for surveillance purposes. The results were structured across six thematic categories: legal environment, management, processes, technology, manpower, and data.

Legal environment

The legal environment is one of the main barriers to data integration. There is no clear legal basis for linking data across systems. As a result, institutions apply strict protection rules and avoid sharing data for public health purposes. A clear legal framework is needed.

Management

There is no national policy for sharing and integrating health data. This gap has led to uncoordinated systems, developed separately by different institutions.

We noted issues related to the lack of mandatory regulation. When data submission or case notification was not legally required (e.g. e-vaccination card or rotavirus, not covered by EU surveillance), it was often deprioritised in practice. There are also legal and ethical concerns about linking anonymous data, which could risk re-identification.

Processes

Health-related data systems operate in silos. Most were developed independently and designed to work on their own. They collect data in isolation, without coordination with other sources.

In official statistical survey systems, basic information on collected data is generally easily accessible. These systems follow standardized forms with defined variables and structure.

Surveillance relies on limited data reported by physicians and laboratories at the notification stage. This is usually done using a uniform disease form. Additional steps are often required, such as contacting hospitals to complete missing details. This increases the workload.

In many cases, notifications are still paper-based. Local public health staff must manually enter them into electronic systems.

Anonymized data collected in specific contexts (e.g. hospital morbidity studies) cannot be reused. Legal and ethical concerns prevent linking these datasets for broader surveillance purposes.

Technology

The technological landscape of health data systems in Poland is heterogeneous. Systems were developed at various times for institution-specific purposes - with no unified standards for interoperability.

Institutions also use different models to manage their systems. Some rely on in-house IT staff. Others outsource to external service providers. These differences effect costs and make integration between systems more difficult.

Manpower

Physicians and laboratory staff responsible for notifying cases are often overburdened. This limits their capacity to contribute meaningfully to surveillance efforts. Notification is often perceived as an administrative task rather than a public health function.

There is limited awareness of how surveillance data can support public health action. Legal rules on data protection, like the GDPR, are interpreted differently across institutions. This creates uncertainty and makes staff cautious about sharing patient data.

Parts of the reporting process that are not mandatory are often omitted. This includes optional fields and electronic forms. Even when digital tools are available, they are rarely used unless required. Paper-based reporting remains common. Local public health authorities must re-enter data manually, which adds to their workload.

Differences in how systems are maintained (in-house vs. outsourced) effect how they can be updated and adapted.

Data

Data-related issues can be a significant barrier to integration and analysis. Values can be missing or inconsistent across systems.

Variables can be defined differently, using distinct formats. This can make it difficult to combine or compare information.

Metadata can be incomplete or unclear. Differences in coding or structure can lead to errors and increase the effort needed for alignment.

Concerns about possible re-identification can also limit how anonymised data can be reused for broader public health purposes.

3.4.3. Impact

In Poland, a process has been initiated to assess legal gaps in health data integration for epidemiological surveillance. It includes reviewing current laws on data sharing by public institutions and linking them across different systems. This aim is to support future legal changes. The identified gaps will be addressed through amendments to the relevant legislation. These activities are part the PNEWRS project (“Improving and strengthening national surveillance systems by implementing IT and training solutions for All Hazards Early Warning” <https://www.pzh.gov.pl/english/>). The project is co-funded by the European Commission and the Ministry of Health, and managed by the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA).

3.4.4. Lessons learned

1. Existing systems contain valuable data that can support epidemiological surveillance.
2. Lack of clear legal regulations is the main barrier. There is no clear legal basis for linking individual health data across systems. As a result, institutions avoid sharing data - even for public health purposes.
3. Systems operate in isolation. Systems were developed independently and are not designed to work together. There are no coordination mechanisms or data exchange pathways between them.
4. Lack of legal obligation leads to lower priority. If reporting or the use of a system is not mandatory, data is often incomplete or missing.
5. Manual data entry and re-entry increases workload. The same information must be entered separately into unconnected systems. Paper forms still need to be entered manually.

3.4.5. Recommendations

1. Advocate for a clear EU-level legal framework to support health data integration. A clear European framework should explicitly enable the use of routinely collected data for public health purposes - including the linkage of personal data across systems.
2. Initiate structured intersectoral collaboration. It is essential to enhance dialogue among public health institutions, IT system owners, legal experts, and public authorities to align common goals and define areas of responsibility.
3. Invest in technical capacity. Strengthen the ability of public health institutions to improve IT infrastructure, to implement interoperable solutions, and to build staff expertise in data management and analysis.

3.4.6. Core messages

- Data integration requires clear legal frameworks. The pilot showed that without a clear legal basis, linking health data across systems is not feasible.
- Surveillance can benefit from reusing existing systems and routinely collected health data originally intended for other primary purposes.

4. Training package

On 25th June 2025, we organised a UNITED4Surveillance Webinar titled "Surveillance of severe infections that lead to hospitalisation - Reflections on Challenges & Lessons Learnt". In the webinar, speakers from the Netherlands and Poland shared their thoughts on the main obstacles, drivers and possible solutions of a well-functioning surveillance system. Italy, Latvia and Norway discussed the topics of legal issues, data ownership and integration of further data sources. Finally, Finland, Malta and Slovenia shared their ideas and use of end point definitions.

The aim of the webinar was to disseminate information on the lessons learned from the perspective of eight countries. This webinar was for persons with a basic understanding of infectious diseases, and interest in hospital surveillance. 102 persons registered for the event and 80 attended. The Webinar was recorded and is available in the ECDC Learning Platform at <https://learning.ecdc.europa.eu/enrol/index.php?id=1141>. An Evaluation Survey was sent for the attendees to gauge their opinion and experience.

5. Deviations from the work plan

There were no deviations from the work plan.

6. List of abbreviations/glossary

AI: Artificial Intelligence
AMR: Antimicrobial Resistance
APACHE: Acute Physiology and Chronic Health Evaluation
ECDC: European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control
EHDS: European Health Data Space
EHR: Electronic Health Record
EU: European Union
GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation
HIS: Hospital Information System
ICD: International Classification of Diseases
ICD-10: International Classification of Diseases – Tenth Revision
ICT: Information and Communication Technology
ICU: Intensive Care Unit
IT: Information Technology
LIS: Laboratory Information System
NLP: Natural Language Processing
RSV: Respiratory Syncytial Virus
SARI: Severe Acute Respiratory Infection
SARS: Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome
S2S: System-to-System